

Prescription Audit Study From a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Telangana

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Abstract:

Background: The inappropriate use of drugs is a global health problem, especially in developing country like India. Irrational prescriptions have an ill effect on health as well as health-care expenditure. Prescription auditing is a crucial tool to improve the quality of prescriptions, which in turn improves the quality of health care provided.

Methods: This observational cross-sectional study was conducted for a period of one month in GMC, GGH, Nalgonda. All prescriptions were analysed for Demographic data, medical components and WHO core drug use indicators. The obtained data was expressed in percentage and frequency.

Results & Conclusion: The prescribing practices in this study were good regarding mentioning of general details of patients and hospital, and satisfactory regarding handwriting legibility of physicians and average number of drugs prescribed per prescription.

Keywords: Prescription, India, Health care.

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Introduction

- The inappropriate use of drugs is a global health problem, especially in developing country like India.
- Irrational prescriptions have an ill effect on health as well as health-care expenditure.
- Prescription auditing is an important tool to improve the quality of prescriptions, which in turn improves the quality of health care provided.[1]
- Worldwide more than 50% of all medicines are prescribed, dispensed, or sold inappropriately.
- 50% of patients fail to take them correctly.

Aims and Objectives

1. To study the data on drug prescription pattern,
2. To analyse the prescriptions according to WHO core drug use indicators. [2]

Material and Methods

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted for a period of one month in GMC, GGH, Nalgonda. After approval from Institutional Ethics committee, the OP Prescriptions were collected irrespective of clinical departments. All

prescriptions were analysed for Demographic data, medical components and WHO core drug use indicators. The obtained data was expressed in percentage and frequency.

The WHO drug use indicators [2] which include three groups

1. Prescribing Indicators

- Average number of drugs per prescription.
- Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name.
- Percentage of prescriptions containing antimicrobial agents (antibiotics).
- Percentage of injections per prescription.
- Percentage of drugs prescribed from the EDL. (Essential drug List)

2. Patient Care Indicators

- Average consultation time.
- Average dispensing time.
- Percentage of drugs dispensed.
- Percentage of drugs adequately labelled.
- Patient's knowledge of correct dosage.

3. Health Facility Indicators

- Availability of copies of EDL (Essential drug List) in all OPDs.
- Availability of key drugs.

Table 1: Medical components of prescription percentage

Medical components of prescription	Percentage
Diagnosis	64%
History	56%
Examination	86%
Investigation	89%
correct dose and diagnosis and dosage	96%
Duration of treatment	62%
Follow up advice	55%
Reason for referral	35%
Legible handwriting	92%
Legible signature	87%
Doctor registration number	1%

Figure 1: Medical components of prescription

Table 2: Age of patients with frequency

Age of patients	Frequency
<20	18%
21-30	21%
31-40	27%
41-50	12%
51-60	15%
>60	7%

Figure 2: Age Distribution

Table 3: Most common group of drugs prescribed with frequency

Most common group of drugs prescribed	Frequency (%)
Creams, gels, lotions etc.	17.50%
PPIs	15%
Antibiotics	13.80%
Analgesics	11%
Multivitamins	10.60%
Antihistaminic	7.70%
Gabapentin	4%
Calcium	2.80%
Laxatives	1.60%
Paracetamol	3.20%
Miscellaneous	12.10%

Figure 3: Most common group of drugs prescribed

Table 4: Most common antibiotics

Most common Antibiotics	Frequency (%)
Ofloxacin	11(32.3%)
Augmentin	5(14.7%)
Metrogl	4(11.7%)
Taxim	4(11.7%)
Other Antibiotics	10(29.4%)

Figure 4: Most common antibiotics

1. Prescribing indicators

Table 5: Prescribing indicators

Prescribing indicators	No. (%)
Average number of drugs per prescription	2.43
Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name	79
Percentage of Prescriptions containing antimicrobial agents (antibiotics)	38
percentage of injections per prescription	0.38
Percentage of drugs prescribed from the EDL	79

2. Patient care indicators

Table 6: Patient care indicators

Average consultation time	2 minutes
Average dispensing time	1.5 minutes
Percentage of drugs actually dispensed	76%
Percentage of drugs adequately labelled	79%
Patients' knowledge of correct dosage	49%

3. Health facility indicators

Table 7: Health facility indicators

Availability of copy of essential drugs list in all OPDs	79%
Availability of key drugs	94%

Discussion

- The average no. of drugs is (2.43) /encounter (our study)
 - Vs drug use pattern in secondary level hospitals (3.1). [3]
 - Study of assessment of drug use pattern using WHO prescribing indicators at Kathmandu, Nepal (1.9). [4]

This parameter is a measure for polypharmacy. Polypharmacy increases healthcare cost and adverse drug reactions.

- Percentage of drugs by Generic name 79% (our study).

Ajar Kumar Sahoo et al in retrospective analysis of drug prescription statistics in a tertiary care Centre in India - 50%. [5]

Another study by Mukesh Sharma et al conducted in north India got use of generic names 68.5%. [6]

- In our study, the percentage of prescriptions containing antibiotics was 38%.
 - Vs antibiotic by Tulika Singh et al was 52.5%. [1]

- A study by Sujith J. Chandy et al, in Vellore, the percentage of encounter with antibiotics was 40.9%. [7]
- Bhavesh k. Lalan, et al, In a tertiary care teaching hospital in Maharashtra 46.17%. [8]
- 4. In our study the percentage of drugs from EDL (Essential drug List) India was 79%.
- A study by Jhaj R, Banerjee A et al the percentage of drugs from EDL was 69%. [9]
- Another study by Arora et al percentage of drugs from EDL is 51.75%. [10]
- 5. Average consultation time 2 mins. (our study).
- BA Ahmed et al in assessment of patient waiting and consultation time in a primary health care clinic -11 min. [11]
- T. Singh et al showed 2.8 min. [1]
- Another study by Mukesh Sharma conducted in north India 7.3 min. [6]
- 6. Average dispensing time 1.5 min (our study).
- Amitabha Chattopadhyay et al conducted in Kolkata got 4.3 min. [12]

Conclusion

- The prescribing practices in this study are satisfactory as the usage of antibiotics are according to WHO guidelines, there is no polypharmacy and awareness about the essential drug list.
- Our study explains the need to increase the consultancy time, to write the registration number of doctors in the op prescription and to increase the awareness of patient knowledge of correct dosage by utilising pharmacovigilance week, conducting rural health programmes etc.

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